

Comment on “Homophily and Transitivity in Dynamic Network Formation”

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April 13, 2026

Abstract

This comment discusses “Homophily and Transitivity in Dynamic Network Formation.” I highlight its core econometric contribution and suggest two directions of extension.

This paper makes a major contribution to dynamic network econometrics. Its central achievement is to bring fixed-effects identification ideas from dynamic discrete choice into a dynamic network formation model. Introducing fixed effects in such a model allows one to distinguish transitivity (a structural taste for closure) from homophily (sorting on latent similarity). In particular, the paper studies the dynamic undirected network formation model

$$D_{ijt} = 1 \{ \alpha_0 D_{ij,t-1} + \beta_0 R_{ij,t-1} + A_{ij} \geq U_{ijt} \}, \quad (1)$$

where D_{ijt} is one if agents i and j are friends at time t , $R_{ij,t-1}$ counts common friends of i and j , A_{ij} captures dyad-specific persistent heterogeneity, and U_{ijt} is an idiosyncratic error term. The paper develops identification strategies for α_0 and β_0 , the latter allows one to assess the importance of transitivity in network formation directly.

My comments have two parts. First, I compare the network setting with the standard dynamic binary choice model and highlight the key challenges in the former. Second, I suggest two directions for extension.

*I have used ChatGPT 5.4, Claude Opus 4.6, Claude Sonnet 4.6. Exactly which is chosen automatically by Visual Studio Code. AI tools have been used to generate Matlab code for the simulation results, for proofreading, and for troubleshooting LaTeX compiling issues.

1. Key Challenges and Innovations

In single-agent dynamic binary choice models, we have

$$D_{it} = 1\{\alpha_0 D_{i,t-1} + \gamma_0 X_{it} + A_i \geq U_{it}\}. \quad (2)$$

The main source of endogeneity is the lagged dependent variable, which creates a feedback loop between past choices and current unobserved heterogeneity. The now standard solution due to Honoré and Kyriazidou (2000) is to find pairs of histories that differ in the timing of a single switch, so that the fixed effects cancel out in a logit conditional likelihood ratio.

Specifically, with three time periods, one considers the event $E_i(d_0, d_3) = E_{i1}(d_0, d_3) \cup E_{i2}(d_0, d_3)$ where

$$E_{i1}(d_0, d_3) = \{D_{i0} = d_0, D_{i1} = 1, D_{i2} = 0, D_{i3} = d_3, X_{i2} = X_{i3}\}, \quad (3)$$

$$E_{i2}(d_0, d_3) = \{D_{i0} = d_0, D_{i1} = 0, D_{i2} = 1, D_{i3} = d_3, X_{i2} = X_{i3}\}. \quad (4)$$

It is easy to verify that

$$P(E_{i1}(d_0, d_3)|A_i, E_i(d_0, d_3), X_{i2} = X_{i3}) = \frac{\frac{\Lambda(\alpha_0 d_0 + \gamma_0 X_{i1} + A_i)}{\Lambda(\alpha_0 d_3 + \gamma_0 X_{i2} + A_i)}}{1 + \frac{\Lambda(\alpha_0 d_0 + \gamma_0 X_{i1} + A_i)}{\Lambda(\alpha_0 d_3 + \gamma_0 X_{i2} + A_i)}}, \quad (5)$$

where $\Lambda(u) = F(u)/(1 - F(u))$ is the log-odds function of the error term U_{it} .

In the logit model, $\Lambda(u) = \exp(u)$, and thus A_i cancels out in the odds ratio of E_{i1} to E_{i2} . That gives us the conditional likelihood:

$$\mathcal{L}(\alpha, \gamma) = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{\exp(\alpha(D_{i0} - D_{i3}) + \gamma'(X_{i1} - X_{i2}))^{E_{i1}}}{(1 + \exp(\alpha(D_{i0} - D_{i3}) + \gamma'(X_{i1} - X_{i2})))^{E_i}}, \quad (6)$$

which does not depend on the fixed effects A_i .

Even without the logit assumption, (5) implies that

$$\begin{aligned} P(E_{i1}(d_0, d_3)|X_{i2} = X_{i3}) &\geq P(E_{i2}(d_0, d_3)|X_{i2} = X_{i3}) \\ \text{if and only if } &\alpha_0(d_0 - d_3) + \gamma'_0(X_{i1} - X_{i2}) \geq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

for all d_0, d_3 . These maximum-score-type conditions can identify the parameters up to scale under support conditions on $X_{i1} - X_{i2}$.

In the network model (1), the presence of the transitivity term $R_{ij,t-1}$ creates a more complex feedback loop. The formation of a link between i and j at time t depends not only on their past link status but also on the number of common friends they had at $t-1$. This means that the history of link formation across all dyads affects the current link probability for any given dyad. As a result, one cannot simply look at events regarding the timing of link formation for a single dyad but instead have to consider the network-wide dependence structure.

The paper’s first contribution is to show that, despite the complex feedback among dyads, one can still define an appropriate conditioning set given which the conditional likelihood does not depend on the dyad-specific fixed effects A_{ij} . The key insight is to stop working at the individual dyad event level and instead move to the joint distribution of the entire network path. At that level, one can identify sufficient statistics for the high-dimensional incidental parameters and then construct conditional likelihood objects that remove fixed effects. This is a substantial technical contribution in its own right.

The second advance is even more important. It is motivated by the complexity of the conditioning set derived from the joint distribution of the entire network path. While that conditioning set eliminates fixed effects, it is computationally difficult to implement in practice. Moreover, it also lacks transparency regarding the source of identification.

The paper therefore takes a further step to define a substructure of the network, namely the identifying star system. This is a collection of dyads with a center agent. In a three-period setting, the neighborhood of the dyads in the star system is maintained to be stable, and the links in the star system are switched from period 1 to period 2.

Then the link history of the identifying star system can be studied in isolation, much like the single-agent histories in the standard dynamic binary choice model. This is a powerful idea and achieves two major goals. First, it provides a transparent source of identification: the variation in the star system’s link history generates the variation needed to identify α_0 and β_0 . Second, it defines conditioning events that are much more tractable, allowing feasible estimation and inference.

I briefly review the key calculations to help readers appreciate the logic. Let \mathcal{S} denote an identifying star system. Then, for each agent forming the dyads in the system, their links to each other except to the star center and to the outside world are held fixed. However, the dyads in \mathcal{S} can change. In particular, from period 1 to period 2, the links in \mathcal{S} are switched. For example, if d_0, d_1, d_2, d_3 are the link histories of the dyads in \mathcal{S} . Then we have $d_{ij1} = 1 - d_{ij2}$ for all $ij \in \mathcal{S}$.

Using the identifying star-system, the paper defines two events:

$$\begin{aligned} E_S(d_0, d_1, d_2, d_3) &= \{D_{ij0} = d_{ij0}, D_{ij1} = d_{ij1}, D_{ij2} = d_{ij2}, D_{ij3} = d_{ij3} \text{ for all } ij \in S\} \\ E_S(d_0, d_2, d_1, d_3) &= \{D_{ij0} = d_{ij0}, D_{ij1} = d_{ij2}, D_{ij2} = d_{ij1}, D_{ij3} = d_{ij3} \text{ for all } ij \in S\} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Let $E_S(d_0, d_3|d_1, d_2) = E_S(d_0, d_1, d_2, d_3) \cup E_S(d_0, d_2, d_1, d_3)$, and $A_S = \{A_{ij} : ij \in S\}$. Then we have the following conditional probabilities:

$$\begin{aligned} &P(E_S(d_0, d_1, d_2, d_3)|A_S, D_{-S}) \\ &= \Pi(d_0, A_S) \prod_{ij \in S} F(\alpha_0 d_{ij0} + \beta_0 r_{ij0} + A_{ij})^{d_{ij1}} (1 - F(\alpha_0 d_{ij0} + \beta_0 r_{ij0} + A_{ij}))^{1-d_{ij1}} \times \\ &\quad F(\alpha_0 d_{ij1} + \beta_0 r_{ij1} + A_{ij})^{d_{ij2}} (1 - F(\alpha_0 d_{ij1} + \beta_0 r_{ij1} + A_{ij}))^{1-d_{ij2}} \times \\ &\quad F(\alpha_0 d_{ij2} + \beta_0 r_{ij2} + A_{ij})^{d_{ij3}} (1 - F(\alpha_0 d_{ij2} + \beta_0 r_{ij2} + A_{ij}))^{1-d_{ij3}}. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

An analogous expression holds for $P(E_S(d_0, d_2, d_1, d_3)|A_S, D_{-S})$. The key point is that the ratio of these two probabilities depends on A_{ij} 's only through the odds ratios. Specifically, it can be derived that

$$\begin{aligned} &P(E_S(d_0, d_1, d_2, d_3)|A_S, D_{-S})/P(E_S(d_0, d_3|d_1, d_2)|A_S, D_{-S}) \\ &= \frac{\prod_{ij \in S} \left(\frac{\Lambda(\alpha_0 d_{ij0} + \beta_0 r_{ij0} + A_{ij})}{\Lambda(\alpha_0 d_{ij2} + \beta_0 r_{ij2} + A_{ij})} \right)^{d_{ij1}} \left(\frac{\Lambda(\alpha_0 d_{ij1} + \beta_0 r_{ij1} + A_{ij})}{\Lambda(\alpha_0 d_{ij2} + \beta_0 r_{ij2} + A_{ij})} \right)^{d_{ij2} - d_{ij3}}}{1 + \prod_{ij \in S} \left(\frac{\Lambda(\alpha_0 d_{ij0} + \beta_0 r_{ij0} + A_{ij})}{\Lambda(\alpha_0 d_{ij2} + \beta_0 r_{ij2} + A_{ij})} \right)^{d_{ij1}} \left(\frac{\Lambda(\alpha_0 d_{ij1} + \beta_0 r_{ij1} + A_{ij})}{\Lambda(\alpha_0 d_{ij2} + \beta_0 r_{ij2} + A_{ij})} \right)^{d_{ij2} - d_{ij3}}}. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

In the logit case, $\Lambda(u) = \exp(u)$ and A_{ij} 's cancel out. Using these conditional probabilities, one can form conditional likelihood by collecting all the identifying star systems in the data. The resulting likelihood depends on α_0 and β_0 but not on A_{ij} 's, allowing for consistent estimation and inference.

The identifying-star systems also makes the source of identification transparent. For example suppose that we focus on all the identifying star-systems with $d_{ij2} = d_{ij3}$ for all $ij \in \mathcal{S}$. Then, the variation of $d_{ij2} - d_{ij0}$ and $r_{ij2} - r_{ij0}$ identifies the parameters. This logic also can lead to potentially semi-parametric identification and estimation without the logit assumption.

2. Going Forward

A useful extension to the framework is to allow the transitivity channel to enter as $\beta_0 g(R_{ij,t-1})$, that is, to allow $R_{ij,t-1}$ to enter nonlinearly. This is not only a functional-form issue. Since $R_{ij,t-1}$ scales with network size and local density, linear specifications can mechanically generate explosive link incentives in moderate to large networks. A saturating or normalized $g(\cdot)$ may preserve economic meaning while improving stability and interpretation.

Another question to ask is how to use the identified parameters to assess the relative importance of transitivity, persistence, and homophily. Such a comparison does not follow immediately from the parameter identification because the distribution of A_{ij} is not identified.

One possibility is to use the estimated parameters to simulate forward under different counterfactual laws of motion. For example, one can compare the full model with a version where link formation is not allowed to depend on $R_{ij,t-1}$. That would isolate the contribution of transitivity feedback to network dynamics. One can also compare with a version where A_{ij} is held fixed at a constant, which would isolate the contribution of homophily and persistence. Below I outline one such decomposition.

Suppose that the parameter estimators $(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ have been obtained from the full model (1). Start from an observed network D_0 . We can simulate D_t under three counterfactual laws of motion:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{No FE: } D_{ijt} &= 1\{\hat{\alpha}D_{ij,t-1} + \hat{\beta}R_{ij,t-1} + a_0 \geq U_{ijt}\}, \\ \text{Constant } R: D_{ijt} &= 1\{\hat{\alpha}D_{ij,t-1} + \hat{\beta}r_0 + a_0 \geq U_{ijt}\}, \\ \text{Constant } D, R: D_{ijt} &= 1\{\hat{\alpha}d_0 + \hat{\beta}r_0 + a_0 \geq U_{ijt}\}. \end{aligned}$$

Here, a_0, d_0, r_0 are calibration constants chosen to match baseline link prevalence and expected common-friend counts to observed data. This sequence progressively shuts down heterogeneity, then endogenous transitivity feedback, then dynamic persistence.

Since I do not have access to the data, I simulate a data set with n agents. I let links in period 0 form randomly with probability p . I draw A_{ij} according to

$$A_{ij} = (0.33 - |\xi_i - \xi_j|) - \alpha_0 p - \beta_0 (n - 2)p^2 + \log\left(\frac{p}{1 - p}\right),$$

where ξ_i is uniformly distributed in $[0, 1]$ across agents. I do not estimate α_0 and β_0 but instead use their true values. I generate U_{ijt} from a standard logistic distribution.

I summarize two illustrative designs:

Specification 1: $n = 50$, $p = 0.2$, $\alpha_0 = 0.5$, $\beta_0 = 0.3$.

Specification 2: $n = 1000$, $p = 0.02$, $\alpha_0 = 1$, $\beta_0 = 0.58$.

For each design, I track a global clustering coefficient: $C_t = \frac{\text{number of triangles} \times 3}{\text{number of connected triples}}$, and the link survival rate after 3 periods: $S_3 = \frac{\mathbf{1}'_N D_0 \odot D_3 \mathbf{1}_N}{\mathbf{1}'_N D_0 \mathbf{1}_N}$, where \odot stands for elementwise product.

The simulation results are summarized in the tables below. Each entry is an average over 100 simulations.

Table 1: Global Clustering Coefficient Over Time($n = 50$, $p = 0.2$, $\alpha_0 = 0.5$, $\beta_0 = 0.3$)

t	Full	No FE	Const R	Const D, R
0	0.19784	0.19784	0.19784	0.19784
1	0.22365	0.21876	0.20012	0.19749
2	0.25161	0.23778	0.20357	0.19593
3	0.29044	0.26341	0.20360	0.19854
4	0.36068	0.30713	0.20149	0.19932

Table 2: One-Period Link Survival Rates($n = 50$, $p = 0.2$, $\alpha_0 = 0.5$, $\beta_0 = 0.3$)

t	Full	No FE	Const R	Const D, R
1	0.27782	0.27889	0.26789	0.20107
2	0.31372	0.30000	0.26848	0.20143
3	0.35639	0.32437	0.27535	0.19517
4	0.42408	0.36647	0.27361	0.19901

Table 3: Global Clustering Coefficient Over Time($n = 1000$, $p = 0.02$, $\alpha_0 = 1$, $\beta_0 = 0.58$)

t	Full	No FE	Const R	Const D, R
0	0.01995	0.01995	0.01995	0.01995
1	0.02299	0.02215	0.02027	0.02010
2	0.02541	0.02372	0.02027	0.01990
3	0.02794	0.02506	0.02027	0.01995
4	0.03120	0.02643	0.02015	0.01999

In Specification 1, clustering *rises* steadily in the full and no-FE designs—from 0.198 at $t = 0$ to 0.361 and 0.307 at $t = 4$ —while the constant- R and constant- D, R designs remain

Table 4: One-Period Link Survival Rates($n = 1000, p = 0.02, \alpha_0 = 1, \beta_0 = 0.58$)

t	Full	No FE	Const R	Const D, R
1	0.05577	0.05509	0.05115	0.02001
2	0.06380	0.05841	0.05129	0.01995
3	0.06861	0.06107	0.05170	0.02020
4	0.07518	0.06364	0.05176	0.01989

near their initial level. Specification 2 shows a similar pattern. In fact, in Specification 2, the full model displays explosive growth in clustering in future periods, reaching 0.965 by $t = 9$. Clustering in the no-FE design also rises, but more gradually (reaching 0.044 at $t = 9$), while the constant- R and constant- D, R designs stay flat throughout.

Survival rates follow the same ordering. In Specification 1, period-4 one-period survival is 0.424 in the full model and 0.366 without fixed effects, compared with 0.274 in the constant- R design and 0.199 in the constant- D, R design. Specification 2 is similar.

As we can see, in our simulation design, the comparison of the simulate-forward designs reveals the relative importance of transitivity, persistence, and homophily. In both specifications, transitivity (No FE \rightarrow Const R) appears to be the main drivers of rising clustering and link survival. Homophily (Full \rightarrow No FE) also contributes, but to a lesser extent than transitivity. Persistence (Const R \rightarrow Const D,R) has little effect on clustering, but its effect on link survival is comparable to that of homophily and transitivity.

5. Concluding Remarks

This paper tackles a first-order econometric problem with originality and technical strength. The identification strategy is reasonable, and the use of identifying star systems is elegant. My main recommendation is to complement the core estimator with a systematic post-estimation decomposition of network dynamics. Doing so would sharpen the substantive interpretation of “transitivity versus homophily” and help practitioners understand when the model predicts realistic clustered sparsity versus rapid convergence to near-complete networks.

References

Honoré, B. E. and Kyriazidou, E. (2000). Panel data discrete choice models with lagged dependent variables. *Econometrica*, 68(4), 839–874.